

ORION Open Science Checklist

Planning stage:

Have you...

- Consulted non-professional scientists about the aims and impact of the research e.g. patient advocates?
 - You could do this in person or via a survey.
- Written a data management plan which clarifies how you deal with your data?
- Planned a non-academic dissemination strategy?
 - Do you know what your institutions Communications strategy/activities are?
- Considered involving citizen scientists in part of the research?
 - ECSA (European Citizen Science Association) and Zooniverse can advise on this.
- Pre-registered your experiments?

During research:

Are you...

- Keeping an Open Lab Notebook?
- Using Citizen Science to enhance and help research?
- Publishing social media updates on the research?
 - Do you have a professional profile for Twitter and other platforms?
- Securely storing and curating your data?
- Using existing Open Science resources to expand, speed up, and strengthen the research you are conducting?

Publishing and Dissemination:

Will you...

- Publish your results as pre-prints?
 - Are there aspects of the projects that you could publish as single experiments?
 - Would a 'data only' paper fit your research well?
- Put your data sets in a suitable repository?
 - Does your data meet the FAIR principles?
- Publish in Open Access journals?
- Include a layman summary either with your academic paper or elsewhere?
- Contribute to open peer review for other researchers?
- Make your code open source?
- Do public engagement activities, such as local talks, schools, podcasts, blogs?
- Talk openly about conducting animal research?